

Multi-Mode Zero-Knowledge Encryption for Database Systems: A Tri-Modal Architecture with Per-Request Key Ephemeral Processing

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Abstract

We present a database encryption architecture offering three switchable zero-knowledge encryption (ZKE) modes within a single engine: (1) **Full ZKE**, where the server never sees plaintext data or encryption keys; (2) **Hybrid ZKE**, where table/column metadata remains unencrypted for basic query routing while row data is encrypted; and (3) **PerRequest ZKE**, where the client provides an ephemeral encryption key with each request, the server temporarily decrypts data for query execution, and the key is immediately zeroized from memory upon completion. The architecture includes per-request nonce-based replay protection, SHA-256 key hash validation, and memory zeroization via the `zeroize` crate. Individual encryption modes exist in prior art (CryptDB, ZeroDB US10,474,835, MongoDB Queryable Encryption, Microsoft Always Encrypted), but the unified tri-modal architecture allowing runtime switching between security/performance tradeoffs within a single database engine is novel. This disclosure establishes prior art for this approach.

1 Introduction

Database encryption approaches occupy a spectrum from fully homomorphic encryption (server computes on ciphertext, never sees plaintext) to transparent data encryption (server always has the key). Existing systems force a fixed position on this spectrum: CryptDB [1] uses layered onion encryption, ZeroDB [2] (US10,474,835) keeps all logic client-side, MongoDB Queryable Encryption operates on encrypted fields, and Microsoft Always Encrypted [3] offers per-column deterministic or randomized modes.

No existing system allows a single database to switch between fundamentally different encryption paradigms at runtime. We describe a tri-modal architecture that fills this gap.

2 Architecture

2.1 Mode 1: Full ZKE

The client encrypts all data before transmission. The server stores only ciphertext and cannot decrypt without the client key. No server-side search capabilities are available.

- Client derives key: $K = \text{Argon2id}(\text{password}, \text{salt})$
- Client encrypts query and data: $C = \text{AES-256-GCM}(K, \text{nonce}, \text{plaintext})$

- Server stores C , never sees K or plaintext
- Client decrypts response

2.2 Mode 2: Hybrid ZKE

Table and column names remain unencrypted, enabling the server to route queries to correct tables/columns. Row data is encrypted. Basic metadata queries (schema discovery, table listing) work without client keys.

2.3 Mode 3: PerRequest ZKE

The client provides an ephemeral encryption key with each request. The server:

1. Validates the key hash against stored SHA-256 hash
2. Decrypts data in memory for query execution
3. Executes the full SQL query with all capabilities
4. Encrypts the response
5. Immediately zeroizes the key from memory (Rust `zeroize` crate)

The key exists in server memory only for the duration of a single request. Nonce-based replay protection ensures each request is unique.

3 Key Derivation

Separate keys are derived for authentication and encryption:

Algorithm 1 Dual Key Derivation

```

1: procedure DERIVEKEYS(password, email)
2:    $salt_{auth} \leftarrow \text{SHA256}(\text{"auth:"} \parallel \textit{email})$ 
3:    $salt_{enc} \leftarrow \text{SHA256}(\text{"enc:"} \parallel \textit{email})$ 
4:    $K_{auth} \leftarrow \text{Argon2id}(\textit{password}, salt_{auth})$ 
5:    $K_{enc} \leftarrow \text{Argon2id}(\textit{password}, salt_{enc})$ 
6:   return ( $K_{auth}$ ,  $K_{enc}$ )
7: end procedure

```

▷ Both wrapped in Zeroizing<>

4 Security Properties

Property	Full	Hybrid	PerReq
Server sees plaintext	Never	Metadata only	During request
Server stores key	Never	Never	Never
SQL capabilities	None	Basic	Full
Key in memory	Never	Never	Request duration
Replay protection	Yes	Yes	Yes

Table 1: Security comparison across modes.

5 Prior Art

6 Implementation

Implemented in Rust as part of HeliosDB Nano (AGPL-3.0). Key components: `ZkeMode` enum (Full/Hybrid/PerRequest), `ZkeConfig` (mode, replay protection, nonce window), `ZeroKnowledgeSession` (encryp-

System	Modes	Switchable
CryptDB [1]	Layered onion	No
ZeroDB (US10,474,835) [2]	Full client-side	No
MongoDB QE	Field-level	No
Always Encrypted [3]	Det./Random per-col	Per-column
Enc2DB [4]	Crypto/TEE hybrid	Execution path
This work	Full/Hybrid/PerReq	Yes, runtime

Table 2: Comparison with existing encrypted database systems.

t/decrypt with zeroization). Uses AES-256-GCM, SHA-256, Argon2id, and the `zeroize` crate for memory cleanup.

7 Conclusion

The tri-modal ZKE architecture enables a single database to offer Full, Hybrid, and PerRequest zero-knowledge encryption modes switchable at runtime. This disclosure establishes prior art for this approach.

References

- [1] R. Popa et al., “CryptDB: Protecting Confidentiality with Encrypted Query Processing,” SOSP, 2011.
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- [3] Microsoft, “Always Encrypted,” SQL Server Documentation, 2016.
- [4] Enc2DB, “A Hybrid and Adaptive Encrypted Query Processing Framework,” arXiv:2404.06819, 2024.